

ACTIVATING STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING GRAMMATICAL TOPICS

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ABSTRACT

In this article, it is about using methods that activate primary school students in increasing their interest in learning their mother tongue, raising their sensitivity to language, introducing linguistic terms into their speech while understanding the meaning of them, and increasing their sensitivity to language. will be discussed

It is well known that, in mother tongue lessons, linguistic terms are gradually introduced into students' speech while providing them with elementary theoretical knowledge about language. Teachers often use linguistic terminology during the explanation of a topic. However, they frequently fail to address the lexical meaning of grammatical concepts, the educational importance of the topic being studied, or the types of errors that may occur when such concepts are used incorrectly in speech. Teachers begin explaining the new topic without relying on students' prior knowledge.

For example, the topic “The Use of Nouns with Case Endings” is taught in Grade 4. When taught again in Grade 5, many teachers who are unfamiliar with the Grade 4 curriculum present the declension of nouns with case endings as a completely new topic. They focus on teaching the grammatical characteristics of case endings based on sentences or texts. Yet they do not explain the meanings of terms such as *case, genitive, accusative, dative, locative, or ablative*. As a result, students are able to recall the names, question forms, and endings of cases in order, but they do not pay attention to the lexical meaning of these terms. This leads to difficulties in justifying their reasoning during analysis. Even upper-grade students, when asked to analyze examples from literary texts, can mention the names and functions of case endings but are often unable to explain their practical significance.

Based on this, we consider it essential for teachers, during lesson preparation, to clarify the following:

1. Determine the theoretical and practical significance of the topic.

2. Assess the learner's readiness for the topic (according to the curriculum).

3. Divide the lesson into smaller stages based on the nature of the topic and define the objectives of each stage.

4. Select instructional materials that will help achieve the intended goals.

5. Choose methods, techniques, and tools suitable for conveying the topic to learners.

6. Identify the group of concepts related to the topic and develop clear explanations for them.

7. Develop instructional questions and tasks relating to the topic.

When teaching the Grade 5 topic *"The Use of Nouns with Case Endings,"* students' prior Grade 4 knowledge about noun declension can be recalled using the following text:

Books enrich a person's spiritual world. Books hold great importance in human life. Our people have always valued books. They viewed books as sacred objects, as books contain much useful information. We too learn what we do not know from books.

[Kaykovus, 2016, p. 224]

The text is analyzed through the following questions and tasks:

Read the text silently. Identify the repeated word based on the noun question form.

Ask a question to the identified word with the help of the word it is linked to. Read them together.

On the board, the following word combinations appear:

- *kitob boyitadi* (—)
- *kitobning ahamiyati* (–ning)
- *kitobni qadrlaganlar* (–ni)
- *kitobga qaraganlar* (–ga)
- *kitobda bayon qilinadi* (–da)
- *kitobdan bilib olamiz* (–dan)

Students then determine:

- Which suffix links *kitob* to the next word?
- What are these endings called?
- To which word class are these endings attached? (nouns)
- Which case ending appears in three different forms, and why?
- Which case endings differ in pronunciation and spelling, and why?

Next, attention is directed to the meanings of the terms *case*, *genitive*, *accusative*, *dative*, *locative*, and *ablative*:

- Why are the endings –ning, –ni, –ga, –da, –dan called "case endings"?
- Why are the cases divided into types such as *genitive*, *accusative*, *dative*, *locative*, *ablative*? Try to explain the meanings of these words.

Throughout this topic, the lexical meanings of terms expressing grammatical concepts are explained, and students are encouraged to incorporate them into their speech. Considering this, the *pinboard method* is particularly effective in teaching case endings in Grade 5, as it involves several sensory elements (hand movement, vision, auditory perception), aiding memorization, recall, and cognitive processing.

Sample student tasks include:

- How many cases exist in the Uzbek language?

- Who can name the first case, its question form, and its suffix?

Students reconstruct the case table on the board from memory, then recite all six cases in order.

To reinforce the topic, the following sentences may be used, which also foster students' pride in their cultural heritage:

Task Cards

1st card.

Read the sentence. Who is it about? Ask a question using the highlighted word and find the related word.

Bobur Mirzo longed for his heavenly homeland throughout his life.

- Explain the meaning of the words *Bobur* and *mirzo*.
- Which legends about Bobur have you read? What did you learn about him?

2nd card.

We live according to Amir Temur's maxim "Strength lies in justice."

- Explain the pronunciation and spelling of *hikmatiga* vs. *hikmatga*.
- Why is the word *Amir Temur* used with the ending -ning

3rd card.

Our ancestor, astronomer Ulughbek, studied the stars shining in the sky of our homeland.

- Explain the meaning of the word *astronomer*.
- Why is *yulduzlar* used with -ni instead of -ning?

4th card.

Alisher Navoi dedicated his works to this land between two rivers.

- What other forms of the suffix -ga exist? In which conditions are they used?
- Identify the names of the two rivers and the land between them.

5th card.

I was born in such a sacred homeland. // I was born in such a sacred land.

- Explain the pronunciation and spelling of the nouns linked to *tug'ilganman*.
- Why is the speaker proud of the land where they were born?

6th card.

Great figures recognized by the world emerged from my homeland.

- To whom is the phrase *great figures* applied? Name famous individuals from our homeland.
- What synonyms can replace the word *zot*?

As students complete these tasks, they continue to use case endings. Selected examples are analyzed on the board for meaning and spelling. Students' speech is observed, and methodological errors are corrected.

II. Composition Task

Students write a text on the topic "*We Are Proud of Our Great Scholars.*"

This activity helps assess their ability to correctly use case endings in speech.

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